

D9.3 District-level and grid optimisation services – Month 18

Date : 17.02.2026

Deliverable No : D9.3

Responsible Partner : CIRCE

Dissemination Level : PU

Short Description	
This deliverable (D9.3) reports the first implementation of Task 9.3 – District-level and grid optimisation services within WILSON. We deliver an Aggregated Demand Portfolio Manager (ADPM) that performs hourly rolling, price aware and risk aware coordination across buildings, using building level uncertainty envelopes, live PV (Photovoltaic)/price forecasts and Monte Carlo estimation of grid overload probability at the point of common coupling (PCC). ADPM emits per-building advisory setpoints and reasoned recommendations designed to integrate with the WILSON PDH (Personal Data Hub)/federated DT (Digital Twin) and with T(ask)9.2/T9.4 components	

Project Information	
Project Acronym:	WILSON
Project Title:	Distributed data modelling and Federated Digital Twinning for lifecycle data-driven sustainable operation and management of buildings and districts
Project Coordinator:	CIRCE
Duration:	48 months

Document Information & Version Management			
Document Title:		D9.3 District-level and grid optimisation services – Month 18	
Related WP/Task:		WP9/T9.3	
Document Type:		Report	
Main Author(s):		CIRCE	
Contributor(s):		Project Consortium	
Reviewed by:		QUE, UNEW	
Approved by:		CIRCE	
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
V1.0	07.10.2025	CIRCE	1 st draft
V1.1	10.10.2025	CIRCE	1 st consolidated version
V1.2	29.10.2025	CIRCE, UNEW, QUE	Reviewed by UNEW, QUE
V2.0	04.11.2025	CIRCE	2 nd consolidated version
V2.1	10.11.2025	CIRCE	Final version
V3.0	17.02.2026	CIRCE	Updated according to PO's comments

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ADPM	Aggregated Demand Portfolio Manager
AHU	Air Handling Unit
API	Application Programming Interface
BMS	Building Management System
CLI	Command-Line Interface
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DT	Digital Twin
ESC	Electricity Self-Consumption
ESS	Electricity Self-Sufficiency
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
IDS	International Data Space
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
kW/kWh	Kilowatt/kilowatt-hour
MILP	Mixed-Integer Linear Programming
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport

MV-ENM	Multi-Vector Energy Network Manager
NDJSON	Newline Delimited JSON
PCC	Point of Common Coupling
PDH	Personal Data Hub
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
PP	Percentage Points
PV	Photovoltaic
QP	Quadratic Programming
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
REST	Representational State Transfer
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SoC	State of Charge
T*, WP*	Task/Work Package
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UC	Use Case

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the development process and status of task concerning District-level and grid energy optimisation, whose objective is to build and pre-validate the first working version of two main services: an ADPM (Aggregated Demand Portfolio Manager) and a MV-ENM (Multi-Vector Energy Network Manager), both at district-level. For the time being, the complete development of MV-ENM is deferred to the following task and it is now available as a service at building-level in task Smart Sensor Systems and analytics for optimal building use and comfort.

CIRCE's living lab is the location used as reference for all the data retrieved, tests, model training and code runs pending pilots' availability in later tasks. Living lab data is retrieved from its SCADA and pre-processes in a way that multiple buildings can be simulated (same time series with little alterations) thus district-level optimisation can be studied. This applies for both PV generation and energy demand. The other data used is electricity market prices, which currently are retrieved from Spanish providers APIs (Application Programming Interface).

ADPM works at district-level, using inputs coming from task Smart Sensor Systems and analytics for optimal building use and comfort, consisting of hourly demand envelopes for the next 24 hours that include minimum, and maximum estimated by the building and the mode estimated value. The coordinator (ADPM script) establishes a priority on how it issues the buildings: first, checks if there is a high probability of grid overload, if so, alerts the building to decrease consumption at that hour and also specifies the estimated quantity to reduce. If there is no risk, then checks its forecasts for the electricity market, if price is higher than a set threshold, also advice the building to consume less so it can save. In any other case, it will tell the building to be as self-sufficient as possible, and if there is a surplus of PV then charge battery storage or EV. Both options are considered solely as a sink and is not enabled in the version developed in this stage, this will be changed on the next phase, allowing district to add storage as a new feature.

ADPM's impact is measured with a deterministic, auditable KPI pipeline over a fixed July-2022 window: data is aligned and cleaned, then, the tool computes each building's local PV use (with an efficiency capture factor and optional without discharging option), and derive PV ESC-B (Electricity Self-Consumption per Building) and ESS-B (Electricity Self-Sufficiency per Building), reported as district averages and scenario (best, worst and min scenario associated with the demand envelopes given by the task of Smart Sensor Systems and analytics for optimal building use and comfort) deltas in percentage points.

Across the studied month, district ESC-B rose from a baseline 85% to 97.4-99.6% under the tested scenarios. ESS-B increased from 6.32% to 6.85-8.08%, with the best scenario (minimum demand) delivering the largest ESS gain (+1.76pp).

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1. Purpose of the deliverable

This document provides the first integrated version of task District-level and grid energy optimisation within WILSON. Its purpose is to specify, implement and validate the ADPM for the electricity vector, detailing how unified building messages (hourly min/mode/max demand envelopes), PV and price baselines, and a PCC (Point of Common Coupling) grid limit are transformed into explainable, hourly advisory setpoints for each building over a rolling 24-hour horizon.

Concretely, the document:

- Defines roles, data and interfaces between this task and its related tasks: it consumes envelopes/constraints from task Smart Sensor Systems and analytics for optimal building use and comfort.
- Formalises the decision framework: a seeded Monte Carlo estimator of overload probability at the PCC, priority logic for grid protection, price response and PV self-consumption and guardrails that never push a building below its hourly minimum.
- Describes the prototype implementation and artefacts: a Python 3 CLI (and later containerised), configuration parameters (thresholds, seeds, etc.), human-readable logs and machine-readable CSV/JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) outputs that enable audits and reproducibility.
- Presents the pre-validation context (CIRCE's living lab) and the KPI pipeline for ESC-B and ESS-B, including data alignment, quality gates and scenario evaluation (min/mode/max).

This report also clarifies scope boundaries at this stage: multi-vector coordination (MV-ENM) remains within task Smart Sensor Systems and analytics for optimal building use and comfort and is not orchestrated at district level by this task. Storage/EVs are treated as sinks for PV surplus only (no discharge/peak-shaving control yet); market participation and closed-loop actuation are deferred to later project stages. Finally, it sets out assumptions, limitations and next steps (calibration of envelopes, correlation modelling, optimiser for fairness and storage scheduling, and MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport) integration) to ensure methodological and technical continuity across subsequent WPs.

2.2. Scope

This report specifies and validates (see section 3.5) the district-level optimisation service, focusing on the ADPM for the electricity vector. It defines the data and control paths between buildings and the district coordinator and documents the first integrated workflow from unified building messages (min/mode/max demand, PV baselines) and grid/market signals to hourly advisory setpoints that reduce overload risk, respond to high prices, and maximise onsite PV self-consumption. The multi-vector network logic (MV-ENM) resides in task Smart Sensor Systems and analytics for optimal building use and comfort; District-level and grid energy optimisation task consumes its constraints/limits and returns portfolio decisions for building controllers.

(T9.3) Smart Sensor Systems and analytics for optimal building use and comfort

(T9.2) District-level and grid energy optimisation

Figure 1: Scope of tasks.

The document details the data acquisition and pre-processing workflow via the PDH/IDS data mesh: message schemas, time alignment of 24-hour horizons across buildings, harmonisation of heterogeneous sources (building envelopes, PV and price series), data quality checks and traceability. It describes how signals are aggregated at district level, how grid limits and price thresholds are represented, and how reproducibility is ensured (seeds, parameters, logs).

The predictive/decision framework used by the coordinator is then formalised: triangular demand envelopes per building, Monte Carlo estimation of overload probability at the PCC, and the decision logic (grid protection with pro rata reductions and guardrails, price driven shedding, PV-based guidance). The interaction with task including Interface for Asset Management Systems, BMS and Digital Logbook, and task Smart Sensor Systems and analytics for optimal building use and comfort, ensures that building comfort and asset constraints are respected and that recommendations are explainable, auditable, and ready for execution.

Finally, we describe the integration links with building services and the district coordinator (exchange patterns, hourly re-optimisation loop, KPIs and logging), and the pre-validation context (e.g., CIRCE Living Lab/pilot data). Out of scope for this report are the final, closed loop implementations and market participation; these will be completed in next phase once PDHs are fully operational, integrated and tested and demonstrated in later stages.

2.3. Objectives

Table 1: Identified objectives of T9.3.

O(bjective)X	Short Description	Description
O1	Maximise self-consumption of local PV and minimise curtailment/export.	Increase the share of locally produced solar energy consumed within the

O(bjective)X	Short Description	Description
		district and also minimise curtailment or export to grid.
O2	Minimise energy cost given hourly prices and tariff structures.	Optimise building demand in response to hourly electricity prices and tariff structures.
O3	Manage grid events	Protect the PCC by limiting overload risk through probabilistic forecasting and adaptive demand reduction.
O4	Provide explainable hourly recommendations for the next 24h.	Deliver transparent, auditable 24-hour ahead advisory setpoints per building.
O5	Deliver lightweight, deployable components.	Ensure modularity, reproducibility and easy integration into the WILSON architecture for TRL6 testing and later WPI3-15 validation.

2.4. Structure of the document

The work reported in this report is organised into five sections. Section 1 is the introduction and the fifth is contains the conclusions of the development.

Sections 2–4 form the core. Section 2 presents the data and integration fabric (PDH/IDS stack), the reference site (CIRCE Living Lab) and pilot contexts, monitored systems, message schemas (for each building min/mode/max, PV/price baselines), and the data quality/traceability pipeline. Section 3 details the Aggregated Demand Portfolio Manager (ADPM) delivered under this activity: uncertainty and risk model, decision, setpoint allocation with fairness/guards, and how comfort/asset constraints are respected through the interfaces (with MV-ENM logic residing in task concerning Smart Sensor Systems and analytics for optimal building use and comfort). Section 4 develops the flexibility and coordination framework at district scale: detection of flexibility windows, interaction patterns with building services and the district coordinator, hourly re-optimisation, runtime logging and KPIs, and the path to integration and TRL6 testing.

2.5. Relation with other tasks

This task (District-level and grid energy optimisation) is the optimisation “engine” of WILSON. It will consume unified building data and analytics from T9.1–T9.2 via the PDH/IDS data mesh stack to deliver two services: a multi-vector energy network manager and an aggregated demand portfolio manager, which will be finalised in second phase of work package Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for energy uses, integrated in WPI3, demonstrated in WPI3 and assessed for impact and replication in WPI5.

Figure 2: Relation of T9.3 with other tasks and Work Packages.

2.5.1. Inputs from other tasks

- **Work package ‘Baseline assessment and performance indicators of buildings and portfolios’-Baseline, UCs (Use Cases) and KPIs**
 - Ex ante surveys of pilot infrastructure, equipment needs analysis and installation planning: site inventories, controllable assets, comms/protocol needs → defines where this report’s task can actuate/read.
 - Analysis of use & business cases and definition of main system functionalities: use/business cases and actors → which optimisation and flexibility services T9.3 must support.
 - Data handling, cybersecurity mechanisms and compliance for federated and data mesh-based DTs: data handling and cybersecurity rules (GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation), resilience) → governs T9.3 data flows and fallback strategies.
 - Definition of KPIs for WILSON monitoring and evaluation plan development: KPI set → targets for evaluation of T9.3 during pre-validation and demos.
- **Work package ‘Data interoperability for data mesh enabled digital twins’ (Phase I & II)-Data mesh stack and connectors**
 - Personalised Data Hubs (Phase I & II) PDHs: single access points per building. Historical and real time streams T9.3 will consume and write to.
 - Decentralized data and services interexchange framework and access control (Phase I & II) Inter-exchange and access control: blockchain/PKI (Public Key Infrastructure) backed governance for T9.3 API calls and contracts.
 - Connectors to legacy and third-party systems (Phase I & II) Connectors: communication protocols will be tested so it can be read.
 - Data ingestion and system integration methods (Phase I & II) Ingestion and integration methods: message broker + REST (Representational State Transfer)/GraphQL APIs that this task uses at runtime.

- **Work package ‘Semantic and federated digital twins at local and district levels’ – Digital twins context**
 - Semantic Local Local DTs and Semantic Federated district level DTs will provide the semantic/physical constraints and states that inform this task optimisation at building and district levels.
- **‘Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for energy uses’ feeders**
 - Interface for Asset Management Systems, BMS and Digital Logbook: unified BMS (Building Management System)/Asset interfaces and Digital Logbook. Harmonised control/telemetry endpoints for T9.3.
 - Smart Sensor Systems and analytics for optimal building use and comfort: analytics and data that T9.3 consumes for decisions, live communication for decision making information is given to T9.2.

2.5.2. Outputs from this task to others

- **Work package ‘Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for energy uses (Phase I)’**
 - Smart Sensor Systems and analytics for optimal building use and comfort: this task responses to the given information of each district’s building will be used in building level optimisation.
- **Work package ‘Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for energy uses (Phase II)’**
 - Second phase of the task will carry the phase 1 algorithms to their final, version ready for integration. Interface for Asset MANAGEMENT Systems, BMS and Digital Logbook (Phase II) and Smart Sensor Systems and analytics for optimal building use and comfort (Phase II) will finalise the interfaces/analytics this task depends on.
- **Work package ‘Integration of technologies and preparation for large-scale pilots’ integration and TRL6 testing**
 - Deployment and monitoring plan turns work package ‘Baseline assessment and performance indicators of buildings and portfolios’ constraints into a deployment/monitoring plan (UCs, KPIs, data and communications)
 - Integration of technologies integrates this task into the final WILSON architecture and tests end to end workflows.
 - Living lab validates this task against work package ‘Baseline assessment and performance indicators of buildings and portfolios’ requirements at CIRCE’s living lab (scalability before large scale demos).
- **Work package ‘Large-scale demonstration campaign’**
 - This task will run in pilots to evidence KPI gains (Risk avoidance, PV self-consumption, cost savings...) over one year campaign.
- **Work package ‘Impacts and guarantees of replication’**
 - Results from this task will feed technoeconomic/replication studies; assessments use the KPIs established in task Definition of KPIs for WILSON monitoring and evaluation plan development.

3. LIVING LAB AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH (1)

This section presents the CIRCE Living Lab pilot building, describing its physical characteristics, available systems (e.g., AHUs (Air Handling Unit), thermostats, luminaires, motion and occupancy sensors), and the monitoring infrastructure that supports it.

It also outlines the methodological framework that will be applied for the analysis, modelling, and development of data driven energy optimisation strategies based on thermal comfort and operational efficiency.

The Living Lab serves as a controlled yet realistic environment where hardware and software solutions can be deployed, tested, and finetuned before large scale implementation in real demonstration sites.

3.1. Building description and monitored system

The Living Lab is located at CIRCE's headquarters in Zaragoza, Spain, and consists of several offices and technical facilities within the same business area. During recent renovations, various innovative solutions were implemented, all of which are managed entirely by CIRCE.

This autonomy guarantees a flexible environment managed by qualified personnel, allowing for the testing of various solutions in the context of sustainability and energy efficiency (2).

Thanks to its great flexibility and extensive network of monitoring sensors, the Living Lab is an ideal environment for developing new solutions and testing different models of automation and energy optimisation. The combination of live data, device control and integration of renewable energy sources makes it particularly suitable for designing, validating and adjusting advanced control strategies before implementing them in real demonstration sites.

In particular, the living lab provides access to:

- Completely automated offices, with access to electricity consumption, temperature, humidity and air quality.
- Several RES (Renewable Energy Sources) equipment: 14.8 kW (kilowatt) of PV on the roof, three electric vehicle chargers and easy access to vehicles to test and energy storage through batteries (5kW/18kWh (kilowatt-hour))
- A centralised microgrid control that connects and controls all the previously mentioned equipment.

This facility serves as the entry point for the deployment of the WILSON project tools. It acts as a technical sandbox, enabling the testing of hardware and software in real conditions while preventing delays in real demo sites.

Figure 3: External view of CIRCE's headquarters

Since 2022, the Living Lab has maintained a continuous historical record of measurements from multiple monitored systems, all integrated into a centralised database. The main categories of devices include lighting systems, air handling units (AHU), contactors, environmental sensors, energy meters, thermostats, HVAC (Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning) equipment, solar generation units, and the main building energy meter.

Each device type provides a wide range of high-resolution measurements. For example:

- Lighting systems record luminosity levels, detect occupancy (presence sensors), and register on/off states to analyse usage patterns and optimise operation.
- Environmental sensors monitor indoor temperature, relative humidity, and CO₂ (Carbon dioxide) concentration to assess comfort and indoor air quality.

All these devices and sensors are mapped within the building's internal layout, which allows correlating the data with the specific zones where events occur. This spatial mapping enhances the capacity to test specific location optimisations, such as zone-based lighting control, targeted HVAC operation, or adaptive ventilation rates. In any case this deliverable will just consider demand and PV generation aggregated at building-level.

Figure 4: Building plan of CIRCE's Living Lab

By combining these capabilities, the CIRCE Living Lab provides a comprehensive, data rich, and controlled environment that enables the entire cycle of energy optimisation development: from initial data exploration, through predictive modelling, to live control testing; serving as a perfect final demonstrator.

3.1.1. Data acquisition and preprocessing

Data is obtained from a centralised database connected to the building's SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) system, which integrates measurements from lighting, HVAC, thermostats, environmental sensors, solar PV systems, energy meters, and electric vehicle chargers.

The SCADA interface provides both:

- Historical data (since 2022), enabling long-term trend analysis and training of machine learning models.
- Live data (updated every 5 minutes), supporting online monitoring and control actions.

Sensors are distributed across all working zones and technical areas, allowing zonal analysis and specific location optimisation.

Baseline PV vs demand and synthetic upscaling for testing

A first pass on the historical data (2022–2025, hourly, overlap only) shows that the site’s PV generation is negligible compared to building demand: total demand $\approx 106,079$ MWh (hourly average 3.46 MW, P95 12.77 MW, peak 19.95 MW) versus PV ≈ 46.6 MWh (hourly average 1.52 kW, peak 10.98 kW, capacity factor proxy 13.8%). PV provides $\sim 0.04\%$ autonomy and is $\sim 99.7\%$ self-consumed, with ~ 0.16 MWh exported and PV $>$ demand in only $\sim 0.29\%$ of hours. This confirms PV is orders of magnitude smaller than the building load and does not, by itself, exercise export/curtailment use cases (storage control, export limits, tariff optimisation, etc.).

To validate the development across diverse operating regimes, synthetic PV scenarios are created by upscaling the PV time series. This preserves the measured intra-day and seasonal patterns while enabling realistic ‘what if’ analyses at higher PV penetrations.

Aggregation and alignment

- All electric demand meters are summed into a building level active power.
- All PV sources are summed into building level PV active power.
- Signals are resampled to 60-minute timesteps, interpolating small gaps (≤ 2 steps)

3.2. Decision-Making and support framework

Figure 5: ADPM logic

ADPM’s control logic can be seen more visually in Figure 5. The district coordinator looks ahead over the next 24 hours, hourly. For every building, reviews a simple demand range with three numbers: a minimum, a most-likely value and a maximum. You can picture this as a triangle: the demand will not go below the minimum or above the maximum and the

peak of the triangle is the most likely value. Alongside this, the coordinator uses live forecasts of PV and market prices, and monitors the district's connection to the upstream grid (the Point of Common Coupling, PCC) which has a defined power limit L . Every hour, the coordinator analyses this information, provides updated recommendations to each building, and recalculates the plan whenever significant deviations occur each hour.

Uncertainty in building demand is represented using a triangular distribution, written as $Triangular(min, mode, max)$. This means the probability of a demand value increases linearly from the minimum up to the most likely (the mode) and then decreases linearly back down to the maximum. Values below the minimum or above the maximum are excluded. At this stage, each building's demand is treated as independent; demand correlations will be addressed in T10.3.

To evaluate the risk of overloading the PCC, the coordinator runs a Monte Carlo simulation (3) for each hour. In this process, it generates a large number of random demand scenarios (by default 4000). For each one, every building's demand is sampled from its triangular distribution, and the district total is calculated by summing across all buildings. The share of simulated total that reach or exceed the PCC limit (L) gives the overload probability for that hour, denoted $p_{over}(h)$. The average of all simulated totals represents the expected district demand $E[total_h]$. To ensure reproducibility, a fixed random seed is used. The statistical uncertainty decreases approximately in proportion to $1/\sqrt{N}$ where N is the number of simulations.

When the overload probability is higher than an acceptable threshold (denoted τ), the coordinator introduces a safety margin below the PCC limit. Instead of targeting L , it targets $L * (1 - margin)$ to maintain a secure buffer. The required reduction is $E[total_h] - L * (1 - margin)$ whenever this value is positive. This total reduction is distributed across buildings in proportion to their most likely demands, while ensuring that no building is reduced below its specified minimum.

If the overload risk remains below the limit computed with the parameters the use/application has set (safe zone) but the electricity price exceed a predefined threshold, the coordinator focuses on cost efficiency. In this case, it proportionally reduces each building's mode demand by a fixed ratio, again ensuring that no building's demand falls below minimum.

When neither overload nor price trigger an intervention, recommendations are based on solar PV forecasts. For each building, if PV generation exceed the maximum demand, the coordinator advises charging electric vehicles or district battery systems to absorb the surplus. When PV lies between the minimum and maximum estimated demand, the recommendation is to maximize self-consumption by aligning flexible loads with PV availability. If PV is below the minimum, the building is expected to import electricity from the grid as usual.

Forecasting methods are intentionally simple and robust. For each hour of the day, the coordinator uses the median value observed over the last N days to estimate demand, price

and PV. If recent data are unavailable, the system falls back to the most recent valid observation and clips all negative values to zero. This approach provides stability, avoids overreaction to outliers and updates continuously as new data arrive.

Each building's recommendation includes a clear explanation of the decision, along with the main numerical drivers. These include the district-level overload probability, the expected total demand, the hourly price and the PV forecast (in kW). This ensures that all actions are transparent and supported by quantitative evidence.

The process runs on a rolling 24-hour horizon and is recomputed every hour as new input arrive from T9.2. As actual conditions evolve, the coordinator updates its estimated and issues revises recommendations, ensuring that the district remains within its PCC limit, operates economically during periods of high prices and maximizes the use of locally generated solar energy.

For example, consider a PCC limit $L=10MW$ and a 10% safety margin, giving a target of $9MW$. For a given hour, simulations will produce an expected total demand of $9.6MW$ and an overload probability of 35%. If the tolerance threshold is $\tau=20\%$, this risk is too high. The reduction gap is therefore $9.6-9=0.6MW$. If two buildings have most likely demands of $4MW$ and $6MW$, the pro rata allocation is 40% and 60% corresponding to $0.24MW$ and $0.36MW$ respectively, subject to each building's minimum limits.

At this stage, the system computes and exposes these allocations and issues per-building recommendations, including the reduction value (*reduce_kW*) and the resulting target setpoints (*target_setpoint_kW*), together with the associated explainers.

3.2.1. Inputs (per hour h)

- **Building messages (NDJSON):** {"building", "datetime", "min_demand", "mid_demand", "max_demand"}. These are treated as a triangular uncertainty envelope per building for that hour's true demand D , which means the following things:
 - **Support:** $D \in [a, b]$. Values outside the envelope area treated as impossible.
 - **Most likely value:** (mode).
 - **Shape:** probability rises linearly from the minimum demand up to the middle estimated, then falls linearly to the maximum in the range, forming a triangle shape.
- **PV forecast** per building $pv_{b,h}$ (kW).
- **Price forecast** c_h (kWh price).
- **Grid limit at the PCC** L_h^{grid} (kW). In the CLI it is a constant (`--grid-limit`).

3.2.2. Coordinator parameters

- **Overload probability threshold** τ .
- **Margin ratio** μ (*margin_ratio* parameter, defaults to 0.05): extra headroom the coordinator keeps below the limit when overload risk is high.
Target import = $L^{grid}(1 - \mu)$.

- **High price threshold** π^{high} and **shed ratio** r_s (defaults to 0.10).
- **Monte Carlo:** N samples and seed.

3.2.3. Control logic

- **Risk estimation (Monte Carlo)**

For each hour h , draw N independent samples per building

$$x_{b,h}^{(n)} \sim \text{Tri}(d_{b,h}^{min}, d_{b,h}^{mid}, d_{b,h}^{max})$$

And form totals $X_h^{(n)} = \sum_b x_{b,h}^{(n)}$.

Overload probability $g_h = \mathbb{P}(X_h \geq L_h^{grid})$ and expected total $\mathbb{E}[X_h]$ are computed.

- **Decision branches**

- **Overload branch (if $g_h \geq \tau$)**

Target district total $T_h = L_h^{grid}(1 - \mu)$. Gap $G_h = \max(0, \mathbb{E}[X_h] - T_h)$.

Allocate a pro rata reduction by modedemand:

$$\Delta_b = G_h \frac{d_{b,h}^{mid}}{\sum_j d_{j,h}^{mid}}, \quad \text{reduce}_b = \min\{\Delta_b, d_{b,h}^{mid} - d_{b,h}^{min}\}$$

Target setpoint for b : $d_{b,h}^{mid} - \text{reduce}_b$ (not below $d_{b,h}^{min}$)

- **High price branch (else if $\text{price}_h \geq \pi^{high}$)**

Recommend a voluntary reduction.

- **PV branch (else)**

Compare $pv_{b,h}$ to the envelope and give guidance:

- If $pv_{b,h} \geq d_{b,h}^{max}$: charge EV/district battery (PV surplus).
- elif $pv_{b,h} \geq d_{b,h}^{min}$: maximise self consumption.
- else: note "PV below minimum demand".

All recommendations are advisory.

3.3. Data Requirements and live signals

- **Building messages (NDJSON):** this coordinator must receive messages from each building with the keys shown in the section above. The code assumes the 24-hour horizons are aligned across buildings. The communication between building and district coordinator will be studied to be done with MQTT, T9.2 and T9.3 will test that communication protocol.
- **PV generation data:** at first it will be needed PV generation data for creating the model, that will be used among all district's buildings. This approach assumes that all solar panels are in a similar situation (panels not being in too different conditions of light/shadow, tilt...), so using all available data creates a single representative model for all the area.
- **Price data:** T9.3 will retrieve price data from public sources (API that could be esios, entsoe...).
- **Forecasting method:** hour of the day's median over the last N days (*--lookback-days*, defaults to 14). Fallback to last observed positive value.

3.4. Outputs and files

- **Response for each building:** each building will receive a message (see Figure 6) structured as a JSON with the manager advice, following this model:

```

{
  "building": "b10",
  "datetime": "2022-07-20T20:00:00",
  "reason": "pv_excess_above_max_demand",
  "pv_forecast_kw": 72.784,
  "excess_kw": 70.845,
  "recommended_action": "charge_ev_or_district_battery"
}
    
```

Figure 6: Current output of ADPM.

- **Informative logs (--log-file):** per building and hour, it echoes the message and the coordinator response in a human readable way.

3.5. KPIs

The KPIs used for this task were got from deliverable 4.5 (4), where KPIs for the WILSON project are explained in detail.

3.5.1. Definitions and scope

ESC-B (PV self-consumption in %): Share of onsite PV that is used locally divided by total PV generated.

ESS-B (self-sufficiency in %): Share of total consumption that is supplied by local PV divided by total consumption.

Both KPIs are computed as daily energies first, then averaged across the evaluation window to form district and means per building, so the higher frequency will be daily but these KPIs will also be available as monthly and yearly values.

In this v1.0 analysis battery energy is counted at charge time in the local numerator (no discharge model). This is standard for ESC, for ESS it is acceptable if charging is also counted in the consumption denominator (our runs use the default setting that keeps ESS \leq 100%).

3.5.2. Data window and parameters

- **Period:** July 2022 (31 days)
- **Baseline capture factor:** 85%, applied to local PV to avoid an overly optimistic baseline (if we count 100% then there could be no room for improvement on self-consumption)
- **Scenario capture factors:** 100% for min_demand, mid_demand and max_demand.
- **Storage:** disabled (no discharge modelled).
- **Resolution:** series are aligned before computing KPIs.

3.5.3. District-level results

Figure 7: KPIs for each scenario.

Figure 7 shows the headline KPIs.

- ESC-B baseline is 85% (entirely drive by the 85% capture setting) and 97.4-99.6% across scenarios. This swing is expected: higher demand absorbs more PV and scenarios use 100% capture.
- ESS-B baseline is 6.324%, max-demand scenario is 6.851%, 7.456% in mode and 8.080% on the min. The min_demand scenario yields the largest ESS gain (+1.756 pp \approx +27.8% relative to baseline).

ESC focuses on PV, so it rises when load \geq PV, hence max_demand shows the highest ESC. Meanwhile, ESS is centered on demand, so it rises when PV/load increases, either by adding PV or reducing load. Hence min_demand dominates ESS.

3.5.4. Building-level heterogeneity

Figure 8: KPIs per building and scenario.

Two clear archetypes emerge:

1. Load limited (b1, b2, b3, b4)

- ESC saturates at 100% in scenarios (PV always absorbed).
- ESS improves materially with demand reduction: roughly +1.5 to +2.5 pp in min_demand, with b2 \approx +2.49 pp (largest mover).

2. PV surplus windows (b10)

- a. Under min_demand ESC dips below baseline (to ~83.9%), indicating intervals with $PV > \text{load}$ (spillage risk).
- b. ESS still improves (~+1.05 pp), but this site is a priority for midday load shifting or small storage to capture surplus.

3.6. Evidence and auditability

We retain all artefacts required for audits: input NDJSON/PV/price files, configuration (thresholds, seeds), generated logs/CSV (Comma-Separated Values) files. Advisory messages include explicit reason tags and driver metrics to support traceability and KPI computation.

3.7. Notation

Table 2: Notation used.

Concept	Symbol in deliverable	Code argument
PCC grid limit	L_h^{grid}	<code>--grid-limit</code>
Overload probability	g_h	Output of <code>overload_probability_mc</code>
Probability threshold	τ	<code>--p-overload-threshold</code>
Headroom (margin)	μ	Margin_ratio (0.05)
High price threshold	π^{high}	<code>--price-high-threshold</code>
Price shed ratio	$r_{\$}$	price_shed_ratio (0.10)
Samples	N	<code>--samples</code>
Look-back days	--	<code>--lookback-days</code>
Building envelope	$d_{b,h}^{min}, d_{b,h}^{mid}, d_{b,h}^{max}$	NDJSON keys

4. MULTI-VECTOR ENERGY NETWORK MANAGER SERVICE

The MV-ENM is the service that will coordinate electricity with other energy vectors (thermal, storage, EVs, etc...) at district scale to manage reserves and relieve congestion. In this deliverable, MV-ENM is not exercised as a district-level optimizer. Instead, it appears only as an upstream constraint provider: T9.3 receives from T9.2 a per-building 24 hour demand envelope (min, mode and max) and treats it as a black box feasible range when computing electricity vector portfolio advisories with the ADPM. Any multi-vector coordination that T9.2 performs inside a building remains local and is not exposed to T9.3 at this stage.

4.1. Current capabilities

Operationally, T9.3 ingests the per-building envelope alongside grid and market signals, quantifies overload risk at the PCC and issues explainable recommendations per building (jnever below the local minimum). When PV surplus is detected, advisories may charge local batteries and EVs. Discharge is not enabled in this version (no export or peak-shaving from storage is commanded yet) so storage/EVs are treated as sinks only for surplus. No cross-vector states, setpoints or flexibility bids are exchanged between T9.2 and T9.3 at this stage.

4.2. Role and architecture at this stage

Each building publishes its 24h envelope through MQTT communication. The ADPM in T9.3 consumes those envelopes and returns per-building advisories over the same fabric. MV-ENM therefore is present as context (feasible operating ranges reflected in those envelopes) rather than as an active district controller. This separation lets us validate portfolio logic and data flow now (including that simple PV charge guidance for EVs/batteries) while preserving a path to add full cross-vector coordination later without changing the building interfaces.

4.3. What is deferred to WP10

The district-level MV-ENM algorithms will be developed and tested in T10.3. That work will also introduce bidirectional storage/EV scheduling, enabling MV-ENM to actively shift or allocate flexibility between vectors and sites rather than just informing T9.3 through envelopes.

5. AGGREGATED DEMAND PORTFOLIO MANAGER SERVICE

5.1. Service description

The ADPM (Figure 5) provides hourly, rolling coordination across buildings for the electricity vector, balancing three drivers: (i) grid headroom, (ii) energy cost under dynamic prices, and (iii) PV self-consumption. Inputs are unified building envelopes (hourly min/mode/max demand), live PV and price baselines, and a constant PCC limit. Outputs are per-building advisory setpoints and reasoned recommendations that never push a site below its hourly minimum. The ADPM complements the building-level logic in T9.2 and will exchange advice/telemetry via PDH/MQTT interfaces.

5.2. Functional architecture

Loop (hourly):

1. Ingest envelopes per building, plus PV and price histories.
2. Forecast PV and price with robust medians with hour of the day (look-back N days).
3. Quantify risk at the PCC via Monte Carlo aggregation of triangular building distributions.
4. Decide using priority logic: grid protection → price response → PV utilisation.
5. Publish per-building advisories and audit log; right now dump CSVs for KPIs.

The component runs as a Python CLI and will be broker-connected in WP10.

5.3. Cross-vector congestion and reserve management

At D9.3 stage, ADPM treats storage/EVs as sinks for PV surplus only. Multi-vector coordination remains inside T9.2 and is reflected to ADPM as feasible envelopes (min/mode/max) per building. This separation lets us validate portfolio-level electricity coordination now, while keeping a clean path to bidirectional storage/EV scheduling and cross-vector reserve management in T10.3.

5.4. Data contracts and envelope validation

ADPM expects a simple, strict contract from building data providers: a rolling 24-hour horizon of NDJSON, one record per building and hour, carrying building name/ID, datetime and the demand envelope (min/mode/max) in kW. All buildings must share the same timestamp set for the horizon, with no gaps or duplicates, we can see a valid message in Figure 9 and a message with both gap and duplicate records in Figure 10. Values must be non-negative and respect the ordering $\text{min} \leq \text{mode} \leq \text{max}$ at every step. Before running coordination, ADP, validates these conditions and aborts the cycle on any violation rather than silently fixing inputs. Validation outcomes and errors are written to the run log so that data quality issues can be traced quickly.

	building	datetime	min_demand	mid_demand	max_demand
0	Building_A	2025-11-05 00:00:00	50	70	100
1	Building_A	2025-11-05 01:00:00	50	70	100
2	Building_A	2025-11-05 02:00:00	50	70	100
3	Building_A	2025-11-05 03:00:00	50	70	100
4	Building_A	2025-11-05 04:00:00	50	70	100
5	Building_A	2025-11-05 05:00:00	50	70	100
6	Building_A	2025-11-05 06:00:00	50	70	100
7	Building_A	2025-11-05 07:00:00	50	70	100
8	Building_A	2025-11-05 08:00:00	50	70	100

Figure 9: Valid building message.

	building	datetime	min_demand	mid_demand	max_demand
0	Building_A	2025-11-05 00:00:00	50	70	90
1	Building_A	2025-11-05 01:00:00	50	70	90
2	Building_A	2025-11-05 02:00:00	50	70	90
3	Building_A	2025-11-05 04:00:00	50	70	90
4	Building_A	2025-11-05 05:00:00	50	70	90
5	Building_A	2025-11-05 05:00:00	50	70	90
6	Building_A	2025-11-05 06:00:00	50	70	90

1 hour gap

Duplicates

Figure 10: Not valid building message.

5.5. Risk calibration and sensitivity

Portfolio protection relies on a small number of parameters that should be calibrated against historical data (preferably 1 year or more from demand data hourly along the grid limit where the district is based): the overload probability threshold τ , the safety margin applied to the PCC limit when risk is active and the Monte Carlo sample size and seed. The recommended approach is to replay representative past periods with recorded envelopes and limits, sweeping values of τ and the margin to quantify the trade-off between hours at or above the PCC limit and total curtailed energy. Deployment should then select setting and record them with the corresponding performance. If future analyses indicate that correlations among building demands significantly influence the risk of extreme total demand, the random sampling model can be adjusted accordingly, This adjustment could incorporate a shared random factor, representing a common influence, to capture correlated rather than independent demand behaviour across buildings,

These parameters need to be calibrated because they determine how conservative or flexible the coordinator will be when managing demand against the grid limit. The overload probability threshold defines how much risk of exceeding the limit is tolerated, while the safety margin controls how much buffer is kept below that limit when risk is high, The Monte Carlo sample size and seed affect how accurately the system estimates the probability of overload.

Calibration ensures that these parameters reflect the actual statistical behaviour of the district rather than arbitrary choices, using historical hourly data, the coordinator can be replayed over past operating periods while varying τ and μ . The selected settings are those that achieve an acceptable balance: keeping overload frequency within a desired range while avoiding unnecessary energy reduction.

5.6. Fairness and allocation policy

When grid protection is triggered, ADPM allocates the required portfolio reduction proportionally to each building's modedemand for that hour, while strictly enforcing the lower bound given by the minimum demand. This baseline policy is intentionally simple and explainable, distributing the reduction effort in proportion to expected usage and remaining robust to uncertainty and envelope noise. Compared with optimization-based coordination frameworks that rely on detailed cost or utility functions, this proportional approach achieves a similar objective of fairness and efficiency while maintaining transparency, low computational burden, and easy interpretability for operators and stakeholders. Where contractual priorities or critical loads require differentiation, the allocation can incorporate non-negative weights and optional caps per building, with exemptions represented by zero weight. The system logs the effective weights, the calculated reductions and the resulting target setpoints, providing a transparent record of how curtailment decisions were made.

5.7. Degraded modes and fallback behaviour

ADPM behaves predictably when inputs are incomplete. If the price signal is unavailable, the price response branch is skipped but grid protection and PV utilisation proceed as usual. If PV data are missing or clearly unreliable, the coordinator avoid recommending charging actions based on that signal and records the uncertainty in the advisory, Baselines for PV and price are computed as hour-of-day medians over the configured history; when too little history is available, the last known value is used and negative values are clipped to zero. Temporal integrity is enforced strictly: the horizon must contain exactly 24 aligned timestamps across buildings; otherwise, the cycle fails fast with a clear message. Monte Carlo simulation uses a fixed seed so that, given the same inputs, decisions are reproducible. Each cycle emits a log and CSVs (for human and machine respectively) that capture parameters, thresholds and reasons, ensuring that even in degraded modes the system prioritises grid protection and minimum-demand guarantees and leaves a complete audit trail.

6. INTEGRATION & DEPLOYMENT

6.1. Orchestration within WILSON platform

At this stage, the coordinator prototype (Task 9.3) is a standalone Python service (CLI tool or container) that runs locally on demand. Integration with the WILSON platform is planned but not finalised:

- **Planned orchestration:** the service will be containerised and deployed under the WILSON orchestrator. Execution will be triggered by updated forecasts (building demand, PV, price).
- **Data flow:** the service will consume forecast messages produced by Task 9.2 (via MQTT), apply overload/price/PV logic, and publish decisions back to the same broker.
- **Next steps:**
 - Define container image and deployment recipe (Helm/K8s).
 - Connect service to platform MQTT broker (credentials, topics).
 - Register its outputs as data products in the WILSON data mesh.

6.2. Communication protocols & APIs

Chosen pattern. Coordinator ↔ buildings will communicate via a lightweight publish/subscribe messaging layer (MQTT planned). The goal is simple, low latency, isolation per building with retained latest snapshots where appropriate.

Interaction model (conceptual)

- **Coordinator → Building**
 - **Decisions:** hourly recommendations (e.g., reduce load, self consume, charge local storage...)
- **Building → Coordinator**
 - **Telemetry/Status:** measured demand/PV and state of availability
 - **(Possible) Acknowledgements/Constraints:** confirmation of applied setpoints and any local limitations.

Design principles

- **Per-building namespaces:** each building exchanges only its own messages; the coordinator has scoped access to all buildings.
- **Versioned payloads:** simple, self-describing JSON with explicit timestamps and horizons; schema versioning to allow evolution without breaking clients.
- **Fallbacks:** the current I/O (CSV/NDJSON) based in files remains as a development and troubleshooting path until the brokered path is live.

6.3. Cyber-Physical security considerations

Objectives. Protect data and control flows while ensuring safe operation of buildings and the local grid. The approach aligns with three pillars:

1. Confidentiality and isolation

- Per-building segregation of communication; least privilege access so buildings can read their own decisions and publish only their own telemetry.
- No personal data is required, building identifiers can be pseudonymised where policy demands.

2. Integrity and authenticity

- Authenticated clients and encrypted transport on the messaging backbone.
- Input validation at ingestion (types, ranges) and strong defaults (non-negative PV, clamping of values).
- Deterministic, traceable runs; each forecast/decision set is timestamped and reproducible (seeded Monte Carlo).

3. Availability and safe behaviour

- Graceful degradation: if communication or inputs are missing, buildings continue using the latest valid snapshot for a bounded time; the coordinator falls back to conservative assumptions (never pushing below hourly minimum demand).
- Human influence: outputs are recommendations; final actuation remains under building control systems/operators.
- Monitoring and alerting: health signals for both sides; visibility on events with overload risk, schema rejections and detailed acknowledgements.

7. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION & CASE STUDIES

7.1. Method summary (execution logic)

Inputs and forecasting

Buildings send hourly min/mode/max envelopes, PV and price are live hour of the day medians (last N days, clipped ≥ 0).

Uncertainty and risk

Hourly Monte Carlo aggregation of triangular building distributions (N=4000, seeded) estimates $P(\text{overload})$ at the PCC and $E[\text{total}]$.

Decision priority

1. Grid protection if $P \geq \tau$: pro rata reductions toward $L(1 - \mu)$, never below each building's hourly min.
2. Price response if grid is safe and price \geq threshold: modest shed (10% of mode), floored at min.
3. PV utilisation otherwise: charge EV/district storage on surplus, maximize self-consumption when PV within the envelope, flag shortfall when PV $<$ min.

7.2. KPI evaluation pipeline

This subsection formalizes how ESC-B (PV self-consumption) and ESS-B (self-sufficiency) are computed from raw signals to auditable, reproducible KPIs. The pipeline is deterministic and parameterised so runs can be repeated verbatim across sites and time windows.

7.2.1. Inputs and configuration

- **Signals (hourly):** per building load $L_{b,t}$ and per building PV $PV_{b,t}$.
- **Envelope scenarios:** NDJSON with $\{d^{min}, d^{mid}, d^{max}\}_{b,t}$ defining three "what if" demand paths (*min_demand*, *mid_demand* and *max_demand*).
- **Evaluation window:** contiguous calendar range (v1.0 July 2022, 31 days)
- **Parameters:** capture factor (baseline: 85%), optional storage (disabled in v1.0 KPI runs) and whether to count storage charging in consumption (defaults to false).

7.2.2. Pre-processing and time alignment

1. **Resampling:** all series to slots of 60 minutes $[t, t + 1h]$, PV is clipped at ≥ 0 .
2. **Aggregation:** sum all consumption meters per building and sum all PV meters per building.
3. **Gap handling:** gaps ≤ 2 hours are linearly interpolated and flagged meanwhile larger gaps invalidate those hours for KPIs (hours dropped but logged).
4. **Scenario frames:** construct load frames $\tilde{L}_{b,t}^{scen}$ directly from the NDJSON envelopes for each scenario.
5. **Date integrity:** enforce a common set of dates across baseline and all scenarios (intersection). Any loss of coverage is reported.

7.2.3. Local use accounting (with optional storage)

Per building b and hour t , the pipeline first determines how much PV can be used locally without any storage. This direct local use is simply the minimum between the building load $\tilde{L}_{b,t}$ and the PV available at that building, $PV_{b,t}$. Formally, $u_{b,t} = \min(\tilde{L}_{b,t}, PV_{b,t})$. If storage is enabled for a site, the pipeline allocates any remaining PV surplus to charging, respecting both the power and energy limits of the storage and the available headroom. The charging energy in the hours is

$$c_{b,t} = \min\{\max(PV_{b,t} - u_{b,t}, 0), P_b^{max}, E_b^{max} - SoC_{b,t}\},$$

And the state of charge evolves as $SoC_{b,t+1} = SoC_{b,t} + \eta_b c_{b,t}$, where P_b^{max} is the maximum charge power, E_b^{max} the energy capacity, and η_b the charging efficiency. The local energy used in KPI numerators is the sum of direct use and charging, scaled by a capture factor γ that reflects realistic local wiring and operational losses:

$$l_{b,t} = (u_{b,t} + c_{b,t}) * \left(\frac{\gamma}{100}\right).$$

The consumption denominator for ESS-B is the scenario load $\tilde{L}_{b,t}$, optionally, if configured, the model can add $c_{b,t}$ to the denominator to reflect metering arrangements where battery charging is also recorded as consumption. In the v1.0 KPI runs reported here, storage is effectively off, matching the results shown earlier.

7.2.4. KPI formulas and daily aggregation

KPIs are computed per building and then aggregated to the district. For a given building b and day d , PV self-consumption (ESC-B) is the ratio between locally used PV and total PV generated that day:

$$ESC - B_{b,d} = 100 * \frac{\sum_{t \in d} l_{b,t}}{\sum_{t \in d} PV_{b,t}}.$$

Self-sufficiency (ESS-B) is the ratio between locally supplied energy (direct use plus any charging counted as local, scaled by γ) and the building's consumption:

$$ESS - B_{b,d} = 100 * \frac{\sum_{t \in d} l_{b,t}}{\sum_{t \in d} Cons_{b,t}},$$

where $Cons_{b,t} = \tilde{L}_{b,t}$ unless the optional counting of charging energy in the denominator is enabled. If a day has zero PV (i.e., $\sum PV = 0$), the ESC-B value for that building and day is set to NaN and excluded from averages. The drop is recorded in the log for traceability. District-level values are obtained by taking the arithmetic mean across buildings for each day and then averaging over the evaluation window. For each scenario, differences versus the baseline are reported as percentage-point changes (Δ in pp), not as relative percentages.

7.2.5. Quality gates and guardrails

The KPI computation is gated by a set of validation steps to protect data quality and ensure comparability across scenarios. First, envelope monotonicity is enforced on the input messages so that $0 \leq d^{min} \leq d^{mid} \leq d^{max}$ for every building and hour combination. Any violation is rejected with a precise reason code. Second, physical range checks ensure that both loads and PV are non-negative (Extreme outliers, identified either by exceeding site-specific physical caps or by very high z-scores are quarantined and excluded from KPI tallies. Third, clock sanity is applied: duplicate (building, datetime) entries are resolved with a last write wins rule, and every rejection or overwrite is auditable in the run log. Finally, consistency checks verify that totals per day are finite before inclusion, where NaNs arise (e.g., days with zero PV for ESC-B), the pipeline prunes them and records explicit counts so coverage is transparent.

7.2.6. Artefacts and reproducibility

The pipeline produces artefacts readable by machines together with the metadata required to reproduce results exactly. Core outputs include a per-day, per-building table with ESC-B and ESS-B for the baseline and each scenario, summaries by building and for the district, and delta tables that express changes versus baseline both overall and by building. Each run persists a compact metadata record (covering evaluated period, the building set, capture factors, any storage parameters and cryptographic hashes of the load, PV and message inputs) so that the same inputs and parameters yield the same outputs. This determinism underpins auditability and enables straightforward comparison of successive runs as models or assumptions evolve.

8. CONCLUSIONS

8.1. Main contributions

This task delivers a transparent, lightweight ADPM that turns unified building envelopes, PV and price baselines and a PCC grid limit into explainable hourly advisories. Using a seeded Monte Carlo estimator on min-mode-max demand envelopes, the coordinator quantifies overload risk and prioritises actions to prevent breaches, temper exposure to high prices and maximise onsite PV use (always with hard guardrails that respect each building's hourly minimum. The prototype is a Python 3 CLI that ingests NDJSON/CSV, produces per-hour overload probabilities and per-building recommendations and emits reproducible logs and KPI tables suitable for audits.

Against the July 2022 window, the KPI evaluation shows consistent gains aligned with our objectives: district PV self-consumption (ESC-B) rises from 85% in the (conservatively captured) baseline to 97.4-99.6% across scenarios, while self-sufficiency (ESS-B) increases from 6.32% to 6.85-8.08%, with the *min_demand* scenario delivering the largest ESS improvement (+1.76 pp). Full results can be seen at ANNEX A, displayed as table with the values for each pair of building and scenario, showing their KPIs alongside each pp and baseline values. Building-level analysis reveals two practical archetypes: load-limited sites that always absorb PV (where price and grid signals dominate) and sites with midday PV surplus (where charging or load shifting should be prioritised). These outcomes evidence that the ADPM achieves O1 (maximise PV self-consumption), O3 (manage grid events with preventive, fair shedding), O4 (provide explainable 24h recommendations) and O5 (deliver deployable components). O2 (cost minimisation) is partially met via price-triggered shedding, deeper savings are expected once storage/EV scheduling is enabled.

The implications are twofold. Methodologically, envelope-based uncertainty with simple, seeded Monte Carlo brings risk awareness and reproducibility without sacrificing clarity. Operationally, the pro rata reduction rule and explicit floors create predictable, equitable behaviour that is easier for operators to trust and for partners to integrate via PDHs and DTs. Along the way we learned that medians of the hour of day are robust live baselines, capture factors are essential to avoid optimistic PV accounting and assuming independence across buildings can misstate simultaneous risks in weather-driven hours.

Within the WILSON architecture, the ADPM corresponds to the "district-level and grid optimisation service" foreseen under work package 'Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for energy uses (Phase I & II)' and directly supports several UCs defined in the report WILSON use and business cases definition: notably UC2 (Energy monitoring and optimisation), UC3 (Data-driven network asset management) and UC8 (Boost of green energy investments by market actors). Through these links, the ADPM acts as the coordination layer that transforms building and asset-level insights into aggregated district-scale operation aligned with grid constraints. It consumes harmonised data through the PDH/IDS infrastructure developed in work packages 'Data interoperability for data mesh enabled digital twins (Phase I & II)' and provides explainable control advisories back to pilot sites via the same data mesh.

In terms of deployment, the ADPM service is being pre-validated at CIRCE's living lab, with full integration planned within the work package 'Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for energy uses (Phase II)' stack and subsequent validation in work package 'Integration of technologies and preparation for large-scale pilots' and work package 'Large-scale demonstration campaign' across the Swiss and Spanish pilots. According to the project plan, integration and monitoring take place between M30–M36, pre-validation by M41 and full pilot demonstration and KPI assessment by M46. This staged deployment ensures that the ADPM is exercised first in a controlled environment and then in real operation under supervision of grid and building operators.

From a business perspective, ADPM adds value as a "district portfolio optimisation" service that can be offered to building operators, aggregators or DSOs to support local flexibility, grid constraint management and transparency in curtailment. It therefore contributes to the business scenarios related to data-driven flexibility markets and energy communities, by enabling fair and auditable coordination logic that supports contractual differentiation between buildings.

8.2. Next steps

Next steps focus on bringing flexibility assets into the loop, sharpening forecasts and completing platform integration (we will extend the coordinator to actively manage stationary storage and EV charging, with EVs treated as mobile batteries). Control will remain explainable and parameterised: PV-following charge windows with headroom caps, explicit evening rebound guards, per-site SoC (State of Charge) and connector limits and simple fairness budgets so shedding and charging efforts are balanced across buildings and over time. Forecast fidelity will improve by replacing the shared PV baseline with per-building PV forecasts and by calibrating min-mode-max envelopes against recent errors. We will also study the possibility to add cross-building correlations, so overload risk reflects weather/occupancy synchrony across the district. Implementation will be completed within the IDS/PDH stack: we will ship the coordinator as a container, so it runs the same everywhere. It will talk over MQTT using one topic per building, with tight permissions so each site only sees its own messages. The service could also stream simple live KPIs.

Operationally, we will run in shadow mode and then supervised closed loop at the living lab and frontrunner pilots, with deviation detection and rapid replanning when measured behaviour drifts from envelopes. Safety and governance will be strengthened through hard floors at building minima, import/export caps, SoC bounds, conservative fallbacks to last-good advice, data handling aligned with GDPR, parameter change control and broker/connectivity health alerts. Finally, to support replication, we will package configuration templates by building archetype, publish schemas and test bundles for onboarding and document incentive patterns for midday flexibility so PV is absorbed without creating evening rebounds. Together these steps bring storage and EVs (including EVs acting as batteries) into routine operation and complete IDS/PDH integration needed for live, auditable deployment across WILSON pilots.

The complete ADPM service will be fully developed and integrated within the WILSON PDH(IDS stack by M36, with pre-validation results expected from CIRCE's living lab by M41 and final

demonstration and KPI evaluation across the pilots by M46. These steps ensure technical readiness and provide the evidence base for replication within the business models and service marketplace defined in WP15.

9. REFERENCES

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10. ANNEX A: KPIs table for ADPM

building	scenario	ESC-B	ESS-B	ESC-B_base	ESS-B_base	ΔESC-B_pp	ΔESS-B_pp
b1	baseline	85	5,603866645	85	5,603866645	0	0
	max_demand	100	6,133349	85	5,603866645	15	0,529482355
	mid_demand	100	6,75336796	85	5,603866645	15	1,149501315
	min_demand	100	7,511186023	85	5,603866645	15	1,907319378
b2	baseline	85	6,899757601	85	6,899757601	0	0
b2	max_demand	100	7,630626515	85	6,899757601	15	0,730868913
b2	mid_demand	100	8,413377428	85	6,899757601	15	1,513619826
b2	min_demand	100	9,390299958	85	6,899757601	15	2,490542357
b3	baseline	85	5,421189712	85	5,421189712	0	0
b3	max_demand	100	5,92296036	85	5,421189712	15	0,501770648
b3	mid_demand	100	6,524570556	85	5,421189712	15	1,103380844
b3	min_demand	100	7,252464634	85	5,421189712	15	1,831274922
b4	baseline	85	5,05350824	85	5,05350824	0	0
b4	max_demand	100	5,32702166	85	5,05350824	15	0,273513421
b4	mid_demand	100	5,858632418	85	5,05350824	15	0,805124179
b4	min_demand	100	6,544946641	85	5,05350824	15	1,491438401
b5	baseline	85	4,011306083	85	4,011306083	0	0
b5	max_demand	100	4,374205599	85	4,011306083	15	0,362899516
b5	mid_demand	100	4,814641937	85	4,011306083	15	0,803335854
b5	min_demand	100	5,349603087	85	4,011306083	15	1,338297004
b6	baseline	85	4,390197186	85	4,390197186	0	0
b6	max_demand	100	4,655301506	85	4,390197186	15	0,265104321
b6	mid_demand	100	5,123226215	85	4,390197186	15	0,73302903
b6	min_demand	100	5,692329931	85	4,390197186	15	1,302132745
b7	baseline	85	5,745509865	85	5,745509865	0	0
b7	max_demand	100	6,271852307	85	5,745509865	15	0,526342442
b7	mid_demand	100	6,912677678	85	5,745509865	15	1,167167813
b7	min_demand	99,77718571	7,706408428	85	5,745509865	14,77718571	1,960898563
b8	baseline	85	4,394162191	85	4,394162191	0	0
b8	max_demand	100	4,787980228	85	4,394162191	15	0,393818037
b8	mid_demand	100	5,272386409	85	4,394162191	15	0,878224219
b8	min_demand	100	5,86008074	85	4,394162191	15	1,46591855
b9	baseline	85	10,4242602	85	10,4242602	0	0
b9	max_demand	98,73860541	11,73829167	85	10,4242602	13,73860541	1,31403147
b9	mid_demand	96,07034357	12,61275333	85	10,4242602	11,07034357	2,188493131
b9	min_demand	89,91146706	13,13951705	85	10,4242602	4,911467062	2,71525685
b10	baseline	85	11,29701334	85	11,29701334	0	0
b10	max_demand	97,12300863	11,6669556	85	11,29701334	12,12300863	0,369942263
b10	mid_demand	93,06834235	12,27923955	85	11,29701334	8,068342348	0,98222621
b10	min_demand	83,8927092	12,34996857	85	11,29701334	-1,107290797	1,052955229

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101147267